

Personality and Tendency in Deciding to Receive Cosmetic Procedures among Thai Youth in The Bangkok Metropolitan Area

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ABSTRACT: Facial cosmetic procedures are medical interventions which are designed to enhance or improve the appearance of the face. In Thailand, there are limited studies that explore the intentions of Thai youth to undergo facial cosmetic procedures. The research's purpose is to investigate the reasons that make Thai youth and teenagers undergo facial cosmetic procedures. The correlation between personality traits and the tendency to undergo cosmetic procedures among Thai youth in the Bangkok Metropolitan area was studied using an online questionnaire based on the personalities under the Big Five Inventory-10, including agreeableness, conscientiousness, extraversion, neuroticism, and openness to experience. The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to analyze the data. There are 427 participants in the survey with 70.02% females, an age range of 16-18 and mostly students. The tendency in receiving cosmetic procedures is significantly different between genders among Thai youth. The tendency of receiving cosmetic procedures is significantly different among Thai youth with different amounts of income. Agreeable personalities are significantly different between genders, but there is no correlation between agreeableness and tendency to obtain facial cosmetic procedures, and women are more likely to receive facial cosmetic procedures than men do regardless of agreeableness.

KEYWORDS: Big five Inventory-10, Facial cosmetic procedures, Gender, Personality, Youth.

INTRODUCTION

Facial cosmetic procedures are medical interventions which enhance or improve the appearance of the face [1]. Non-surgical procedures use technology to lift, add volume, smooth or rejuvenate without cutting the skin to directly access the tissue layer underneath [2]. It is human nature to always want to improve their appearance and confidence or to reverse signs of aging [3]. Thus, humans have developed facial cosmetic procedures for various purposes, for example facial cosmetic procedures to become an actor or influencer which would help them to increase the chances to succeed in their career. Another reason is to fulfil their personal desires, as this could improve their overall self-esteem and can make individuals feel more comfortable and confident in their appearance.

In this research, researchers would like to study the correlation between personality and tendency to receive facial cosmetic procedures. For example, people who are not confident in themselves may prefer to receive facial cosmetic procedures more than those who are self confident. Additionally, there are few studies that address the intention of Thai youth to receive facial cosmetics procedures. On top of that, we frequently notice advertisements in social media about Thai youth receiving cosmetic procedures [4] along with beauty clinics, which are places where clients especially women, go for receives cosmetics procedure or cosmetics treatment, they often promoting their services such as skin treatment, dermal filler and botox by using young influencer to promote their facial cosmetic procedure services at their centre. As a result of this, we wonder what the reasons that make Thai youth and teenagers undergoing facial cosmetic procedures, and what factors influence the likelihood of them undergoing facial cosmetic procedures would be. Therefore, this research is studied to make Thai youth appreciate and comprehend about beauty and help them to make a right decision if they would like to access beauty industries and to encourage Thai youth to have more confidence in themselves. Moreover, references to facial cosmetics clinics were widespread in the social media and all over around, as a result of this facial aesthetics clinics have been rapidly appearing everywhere in Bangkok and metropolitan areas.

For this reason, researchers took interest in investigating the correlation by using personality traits as personality have defined a person's behaviour and this could be a key factor to inspire Thai youth to decide to receive a facial cosmetic procedure. Beauty is something that every human desires to have to build up confidence and make themselves look as attractive as possible. From the investigation, researchers found that patients who undergo cosmetic procedures have a better quality of life such as an improvement of emotional, mental wellbeing, overall look and improved associated physical symptoms [5]. Furthermore, according to the study in 2023 there are 44% of people who received facial cosmetic procedures [6]. Therefore, the researchers predicted that more than 44% of Thai youth that live in Bangkok and metropolitan areas would likely undergo facial cosmetic procedure due to the influences of social media which amplifies beauty standards and trend as well as there is a growing trends toward self-care so this allowed individual to invest in their appearances and self support. As in the present, receiving facial cosmetic procedures has become more common and popular, especially in youth [7]. In spite of that, researchers have found that although facial cosmetic procedures are popular in Thailand and Thailand has no shortages of experienced and certified doctors with international standard hospitals that that provide a latest facial cosmetic procedure [8], yet there are still patients who not willing to received facial cosmetic procedures due to reason that some individual might already satisfied with their facial appearance or some groups of people still fear from receiving facial cosmetics which will result them in scar or the feeling of pain [9].

Moreover, money has play a big role in beauty industries because not everyone can afford the cost of facial cosmetic procedures [10] as a consequence of cost of cosmetics procedure, the experience of a doctors, cost of material and also there might be some additional cost of aftercare and future procedures that patient might wanted to maintain their new looks as well as the trust of the clinics and doctors that will performed procedures on your face which patient needed to take time to do research and study carefully to guarantee that doctor has fully trained and clinic are trustworthy [11]. In fact, aesthetic clinics or cosmetic clinics were gradually increasing, growing up 16.6% per year in Bangkok and the metropolitan area because of increasing demand of people who prefer to receive facial cosmetic procedures [12].

However, each of the people have different personal traits and different supporting characteristics that lead to difficulty to classify personalities. Personalities are difficult to classify. To handle the issue, the researchers decided to use a personality test named "Big 5 personality factors" [13] to describe separate survey respondents' personality. The reason for choosing the Big 5 personality test is because it is about as twice as accurate as the MBTI [14] and Big 5 personality traits can significantly predict emotional intelligence [15] including openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism when it comes to decision making. In conclusion, other research found that the trend of receiving facial cosmetic procedures is increasing. However, we did not manage to find works that studied the relationship between personality traits and the trend of receiving facial cosmetic procedures. Therefore, our objective in this research is to identify personality traits through questionnaires to determine the trends in facial cosmetic procedures among Thai youth. This research may be beneficial to beauty clinics to understand Thai youth and for Thai youth to make the right decision whether to undergo facial cosmetic procedures.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted to investigate the correlation between personality and tendency to decide to receive cosmetic procedures among Thai youth in the Bangkok Metropolitan area by using an online questionnaire, which consists of 3 sections in the following order: general information, describing personality using Big Five Inventory-10 and facial cosmetic procedure readiness. The first section involved multiple choices, the second and third were gathered through 1-5 Likert scale questions including, with 1 meaning strongly disagree, 2 disagree 3 neither agree or disagree 4 agree and lastly 5 strongly agree. By following the research procedure, each questionnaire was reviewed by the consultant and achieved the Item-Objective congruence (IOC) index score which is equal or higher than 0.5. The data for the pilot test has been collected and taken to analyze using Cronbrach's alpha which is a way to evaluate the reliability of a composite score by comparing shared variance of the items making up for survey, in accordance with the benchmark value of 0.7. Cortina, J. M. (1993) This indicates that the measurement instrument is reliable. The achieved result was 0.905, which showed that the study has high internal consistency [16]. The research was conducted via Google form and was distributed through the Instagram inbox application, Line application and email to request participants to fill out research questionnaires in June 2024. Eventually, researchers collected data from 457 respondents the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to provide the analysis of the data as well as F-test (ANOVA or Analysis of Variance) which was

used to analyze the various types of personality traits by comparing the means of more than one group, along with T-test which used to determined the significant differences between the means of two groups.

INSTRUMENT

Part1: General information

1. Gender.
2. Age group.
3. Current professional status
4. Place of residence
5. Total income per month? (including earned income and allowances)
6. Have you ever received a facial cosmetic procedure?

Part 2: Describe your personality using Big Five Inventory-10 [17]

1. Extraversion
 - 1.1. I see myself as someone who feels more comfortable focusing on their inner thoughts and ideas. (Reverse-scored)
 - 1.2. I see myself as someone who has few artistic interests.
2. Agreeableness
 - 2.1. I see myself as someone who is honest and sincere.
 - 2.2. I see myself as someone who tends to find faults with others. (Reverse-scored)
3. Conscientiousness
 - 3.1. I see myself as someone who tends to be lazy. (Reverse-scored)
 - 3.2. I see myself as someone who completes a task with great attention to detail.
4. Neuroticism
 - 4.1. I see myself as someone who is relaxed and manages my time effectively. (Reverse-scored) I see myself as someone who gets nervous easily.
5. Openness to Experience
 - 5.1. I see myself as someone who has few artistic interests. (Reverse-scored)
 - 5.2. I see myself as someone who has an active imagination.

Part 3: Facial Cosmetic Procedure Readiness Questionnaire [18][19]

1. On the whole, I am not satisfied with my physical appearance.
2. I often get teased about my appearance.
3. I think that getting facial cosmetic procedures is now a very common practice in society.
4. I sometimes feel that my appearance is one of my weaknesses.
5. I think about unattractive parts of my appearance a lot.
6. I think that after getting a facial cosmetics procedure, I would feel more confident.
7. I believe appearance could have effects on my job opportunities.
8. Accepting my appearance will not help much to improve my quality of life
9. After receiving a facial cosmetic procedure, I think that there would be more people interested in me than before.
10. I am often interested in advertisements about facial aesthetics.
11. I am well familiar with facial cosmetic procedures.
12. I often consider receiving cosmetic procedures on my face.
13. I am interested in doing facial cosmetics procedure
14. I have consulted about undergoing cosmetic procedure with acquaintances or nearby people around me
15. I know which type of facial cosmetic procedure will suit me.
16. I have bad experience about receiving facial cosmetics procedures
17. I know which facial aesthetics clinic to trust
18. I would you like to do cosmetic procedure in the future
19. I decided to do facial cosmetic procedures in the future.

RESULTS

Table 1: General information (N= 427)

	Frequently	Valid Percent
Gender		
Female	299	70.02
Male	124	29.03
Others	4	0.95
Age		
12-15 years	174	40.75
16-18 years	181	42.39
19-25 years	72	16.86
Professional status		
Student	394	92.27
Employed	27	6.32
Unemployed	5	1.17
Others	1	0.24
Residence		
Bangkok	215	50.35
Vicinity province	212	49.65
Total income per month		
0-10,000 THB	223	52.22
10,000-50,000 THB	194	45.43
More than 50,000 THB	10	2.35
Ever received facial cosmetic procedure		
Yes	77	18.03
No	350	81.97

There are 427 participants of the survey. The majority of the sample is females which calculates to 70.02%. Primarily the participants have an age range between 16-18 and most of the responders are students. About half of all respondents are from Bangkok at 50.35%. 223 of the participants have an income of 0-10,000 THB per month, which includes from their pocket money and extra allowance. 350 of the respondents at 81.97% have never received any facial cosmetic procedure.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics (Mean, Standard Deviation)

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Agreeableness	427	3.594	0.757
Conscientiousness	427	2.982	0.746
Extraversion	427	3.015	0.628
Neuroticism	427	3.367	0.699
Openness to Experience	427	3.436	0.840
Facial cosmetic procedures readiness	427	2.912	0.674

The minimum score is 1 and the maximum score is 5, where 5 is the highest tendency of deciding to receive a facial cosmetic procedure. The table shows each mean score and standard deviation of 5 different personality traits including agreeableness, conscientiousness, extraversion, neuroticism, and openness to experience, as well as the mean score and standard deviation of tendency to receive facial cosmetic procedures. The mean scores are 3.594, 2.982, 3.015, 3.367, 3.436, and 2.912, and the standard deviation is 0.757, 0.746, 0.628, 0.699, 0.840 and 0.674, respectively.

Table 3: One-way ANOVA (F-test); Gender and Face procedure

	Sum of Squares	df	MS	F	p-value
Between Groups	4.621	2	2.311	5.184**	0.006
Within Groups	188.981	424	0.446		
Total	193.602	426			

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The one-way ANOVA results achieved a p-value of 0.006. It means that the tendency of Thai youth receiving cosmetic procedures is significantly different between genders.

Table 4: One-way ANOVA (F-test); Income and Facial cosmetic procedure

	Sum of Squares	df	MS	F	p-value
Between Groups	6.501	2	3.251	7.367**	<0.001
Within Groups	187.101	424	0.441		
Total	193.602	426			

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

One-way ANOVA results obtained a p-value of 0.001. It can be concluded that the tendency of receiving cosmetic procedures is significantly different among Thai youth that have different amounts of income as the p-value achieved is less than 0.05.

Table 5: One-way ANOVA (F-test); Gender and Agreeableness

	Sum of Squares	df	MS	F	P-value
Between Groups	12.100	2	6.050	11.049**	<0.001
Within Groups	232.153	424	0.548		
Total	244.253	426			

One-way ANOVA results achieved a p-value of 0.001 which means that personalities are significantly different between gender, because that the p-value that archive is less than 0.05.

Table 6: Pearson’s Correlation between Agreeableness and Facial cosmetic procedures

	Agreeableness	Facial cosmetic procedure
Agreeableness		
Pearson Correlation	1	0.002
Sig. (2-tailed)		0.961
N	427	427
Facial cosmetic procedure		
Pearson Correlation	0.002	1
Sig. (2-tailed)	0.961	
N	427	427

Pearson’s Correlation of r value at 0.002 was obtained, which demonstrated that there are no correlation between agreeableness and tendency to obtain facial cosmetic procedure.

DISCUSSION

The study demonstrates a correlation between personality and the tendency to decide to receive facial cosmetic procedures. At present, facial cosmetic procedures have become very common and very popular in Thailand, as well as on social media, a place where unrealistic beauty standards are portrayed, creating pressure for people to conform [20]. Therefore, identifying the correlation relationships will allow researchers to find the reason that will lead to the decision of Thai youth in receiving facial cosmetic procedures along with the understanding of the personality test such as Big-Five that would affect Thai youth to undergo facial cosmetics procedure. On the other hand, researchers using Big-Five as a contributing factor as Big-Five is the most scientific validity and reliable personality test [21].

Firstly, to investigate the correlation between personality and tendency in deciding to receive facial cosmetic procedures, researchers conducted the investigation by using an online survey to explore the likelihood of receiving facial cosmetic procedures of Thai youth. According to Table 2, the minimum score is 1 and the maximum score is 5, whereas 5 is the highest tendency of

deciding to receive a facial cosmetic procedure and 3 is the midpoint to express neutral feelings toward the tendency to receive facial cosmetic procedures. The table shows each mean score of 5 different personality traits including agreeableness, Conscientiousness, extraversion, neuroticism, and openness to experience as well as the mean score and standard deviation of tendency to receive facial cosmetic procedures. There is no doubt that the mean score is 3.594, 2.982, 3.015, 3.367, 3.436, and 2.912 respectively.

As shown in Table 3, gender is significantly different between Thai youth receiving cosmetic procedures and this shows that gender has a significant effect in deciding to receive facial cosmetic procedures. The result the researchers have obtained is similar to the study by Brown A. et al. (2007), which said that females have a higher tendency to choose to receive facial cosmetics procedures [22]. In fact, women worry more about beauty than their male counterparts. Women are more worried about their appearance, their wrinkles, grey hairs if it is showing, their sagging skin and so, women take more care and often visit beauty salons to maintain their beauty appearance. On the other hand, males are not concerned much about themselves when it comes to appearance, they are more relaxed and they are not bothered much about how they need to present themselves to others.

Moreover, according to Table 4, the tendency of receiving cosmetic procedures is different among Thai youth that have different amounts of income, as the p-value is less than 0.05, which is similar to that found in the study from Alharethy SE. (2017) which said that the majority of the people who undergo facial procedures have higher economic status as individuals have greater ability to access cosmetic procedures [23]. Beside that facial cosmetic is not a basic necessity therefore, individuals who receive facial cosmetic procedures should have at least an average income so they would have an excess fund to spend on luxury. Our result is in line with the study from Alharethy SE which has shown that income has significantly related the tendency in receiving facial cosmetic procedures.

Table 5 shows that one-way ANOVA results achieved a p-value of 0.001, which means that the scores for agreeableness personalities are significantly different between genders, as the p-value is less than 0.05. Agreeableness refers to the ability to put others' needs before their own [24]. Table 6 shows Pearson's Correlation with r value of 0.002, so there is no evidence of a correlation between degree of agreeableness and tendency to receive a facial cosmetic procedure. On the other hand, Table 3 demonstrates that there is a significant difference in tendencies to receive facial cosmetic procedures between genders, by which women are more likely to receive facial cosmetic procedures than men do, and because agreeableness personality do not greatly influence a person's decision to have a facial cosmetic procedure, it is not agreeableness that would make a gender more likely to receive cosmetic procedure than another.

CONCLUSION

Our studies have shown that women who are living in Bangkok and the metropolitan area have a higher percentage of interest in receiving facial cosmetic procedures than men as people want to feel more confident about themselves and want to achieve their ideal type of beauty. On top of that, our research has shown that there is a significant difference in tendencies to receive facial cosmetic procedures between genders and among Thai youth with different incomes. In addition to that, agreeableness personality does not influence the tendency in deciding to receive facial cosmetic procedures as there is no matter whether individuals are agreeable or not, agreeableness personality would not affect their tendency to receive facial cosmetic procedures.

Cosmetic doctors should be intimate with their patients personality traits to prevent negative results, so they would know how to approach their patients to make them feel comfortable and give them suitable advice regarding receiving facial cosmetic procedures. Nevertheless, to assure that the clinical profession is able to understand and approach the general population, continuous gathering data should be developed as people with different kinds of personality traits would walk into a clinic and request for facial cosmetics.

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